

WP4 (Taiwan) Method Memo

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How does the Taiwanese Legal System Hold the State Accountability for its Use of Human Rights Justification in its Actions During the COVID-19 Pandemic?

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Executive Summary

This memo provides a comprehensive review of how the Taiwanese government holds itself accountable for its use of human rights justifications through both international and national lenses. This includes an analysis of the legal framework and institutional mechanisms, as well as an exploration of how these oversight mechanisms were weakened during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Until May 2023, Taiwan was one of the few strongholds of zero-COVID with extensive border control and regulations. Due to the unique geopolitical relationship between Taiwan and China, alongside Taiwan's isolated status as a non-member state in the WHO, and its experience with the 2003 SARS outbreak, the Taiwanese government implemented strict border controls and extensive contact tracing measures. Meanwhile, the power of both international and national oversight mechanisms became weak and self-limiting when facing the government's strong and extensive COVID-19 measures.

Taiwan, not being a member of the UN, lacks access to the Universal Periodic Review (UPR) to ensure compliance with UN conventions. Due to Taiwan's unique status, the Taiwanese government could only be held accountable for international human rights by "internalizing" international human rights standards on the legislative level. Nevertheless, Taiwan has established an alternative international review mechanism since 2013. The international review committees, composed of individuals with prior experience in UN treaty review, can pressure the Taiwanese government to comply with international covenants and the UN's COVID-19 Guidance. The National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), as an administrative agency, also serves as a mechanism for supervising the domestic implementation of conventions and a channel for individuals to file complaints. Unfortunately, the NHRC suspended its checking power when the government expanded the digital fence program.

We offer three examples to elaborate on how the domestic oversight mechanisms had weakened during the COVID-19 pandemic, as most of the oversight organs voluntarily relinquished their checking power. For example, as the ruling party, the Democratic Progressive Party (DPP) also has the majority in Congress throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, the Congress readily supported any COVID-19 measures proposed by the administration. Nor did the Control Yuan exercise its power of corrective measures when pointing out that the government's COVID-19 measure violated human rights and the principle of the rule of law. Taiwan's Constitutional Court utilized procedural reasoning to dismiss the request for reviewing the constitutionality of the Special Act.

Civil society has raised concerns about whether the accountability mechanisms during the COVID-19 pandemic can be strengthened post-pandemic. In the first year, we already engaged with civil society to inquire generally about their interaction with international mechanisms and the EU, as well as how these interactions influence their work. In the second year, we plan to share our first-year findings on COVID-19 governance in Taiwan with experts, advocates, and those impacted by COVID-19 measures. We will focus on three groups of people who were particularly affected by the COVID-19 governance in Taiwan: healthcare workers, flight crew members, and local epidemic prevention personnel.

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1. How does the state hold its accountable for human rights justifications

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Human rights development has faced new challenges in recent years. Many actors, including governments, have utilized human rights discourses while actually taking actions that undermine the achievements of current human rights development.¹ This article, viewed through this lens, points out how the Taiwanese government appropriated human rights discourses and intended to legitimize its mandatory measures, which violated human rights protection by the Constitution during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Until May 2023, Taiwan was one of the few strongholds of zero-COVID with extensive border control and regulations. Due to the unique geopolitical relationship between Taiwan and China, alongside Taiwan's isolated status as a non-member state in the WHO, and its experience with the 2003 SARS outbreak, the Taiwanese government implemented strict border controls and extensive contact tracing measures.² Border control alone lasted for 30 months. The facemask mandate was not lifted until April 2023. Meanwhile, the occupation of certain groups considered of higher risk were disproportionately affected by strict measures. For instance, medical workers were prohibited from traveling abroad during the initial stages of the pandemic.³ A two-week quarantine was imposed on individuals who had contact with confirmed cases or returned from abroad. Flight crew were especially burdened by strict quarantine rules.⁴ Migrant workers (including factory and fishing industry workers) faced challenges in adhering to quarantine measures in their dormitory environments.⁵

¹ de Búrca, G & Young, K (2023). The (Mis)Appropriation of Human Rights by the New Global Right: An Introduction to the Symposium, *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, 21(1), 205-223.

² Lee, P.-H., & Kao, Y.-C. (2022). Health Apartheid during covid-19: A Decolonial Critique of Racial Politics between Taiwan and the who. *International Journal of Taiwan Studies*, 5(2), 375-402.

<https://doi.org/10.1163/24688800-05020006>. Loduhoa, A., & Kironka, K. (2022). How Did Taiwan Go from 'Most Affected' during sars to 'Least Affected' during covid-19?: A Comparative Study of Taiwan's Emergency Responses. *International Journal of Taiwan Studies*, 6(2), 291-316.

<https://doi.org/10.1163/24688800-20221249>.

³ CNA (2020702/02). Taiwan bans its healthcare professionals from traveling abroad. Central News Agency, <https://www.taiwannews.com.tw/en/news/3880226>.

⁴ Walker, T. (2022/08/31). Taiwan Pilots, Cabin Crews Bemoan Stringent COVID Restrictions. VOA, <https://www.voanews.com/a/taiwan-pilots-cabin-crews-bemoan-stringent-covid-restrictions-/6724452.html>

⁵ Marschke, M., Vandergeest, P., Havice, E., Kadfak, A., Duker, P., Isopescu, I., & MacDonnell, M. (2021). COVID-19, instability and migrant fish workers in Asia. *Maritime Studies*, 20(1), 87-99. Pandey, P., & Yu, M.-K. (2022). Experiences of foreign residents during COVID-19 pandemic in Taiwan. *Journal of Migration and Health*, 5, 100080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmh.2022.100080><https://doi.org/10.1007/s40152-020-00205-y>. Chan, Y. W., & Lan, P.-C. (2022). The politics of sanitization: Pandemic crisis, migration and

Taiwan implemented nearly the most stringent measures among all so-called “liberal democracies.” In comparison South Korea, which utilized digital measures legitimated by its open border policy and authorized by the Communicative Disease Act revised after the MERS outbreak⁶, and New Zealand /Australia, which had strong border control but lacked the infrastructure for implementing extensive digital measures.⁷ In WP4, we examine the Taiwanese government’s extremely strict measures in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and how they actually infringe on human rights protection while lacking oversight. First, this memo provides an overview of how the Taiwanese government holds itself accountable for its use of human rights justifications at international and national levels. Second, this memo offers a few examples in which the Taiwanese government utilized or did not utilize human rights justifications to justify its measures during the pandemic, and analyzes how the accountability mechanism failed to effectively address potential human rights concerns.

1.1. International Level

1.1.1. Law on Paper: International Human Rights Treaties and the Implementation Acts

The Republic of China (ROC) on Taiwan (hereinafter ROC or Taiwan), a non-member of the United Nations since 1971, was excluded from the UN system and its human rights regime. Following the democratization transition in the 1990s, the Taiwanese government utilized human rights discourses to safeguard and enhance its international standing.⁸ To demonstrate its conformity to international human rights development, Congress (the Legislative Yuan) ratified the two Covenants (the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights). However, Taiwan’s attempt to deposit them in the UN Secretariat in 2009 was without success. Subsequently, the Congress continued ratifying the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) in 2011, the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) in 2016. However, none of the above-mentioned ratifications could be deposited and accepted by the UN.

development in Asia-Pacific. *Asian and Pacific Migration Journal*, 31(3), 205-224.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/01171968221129382>

⁶ Lee, S., Kim, T-H. (2021/04/08). South Korea’s Combating COVID-19 Under the Rule of Law. Verfblog, <https://verfassungsblog.de/south-koreas-combating-covid-19-under-the-rule-of-law/>

⁷ Hopkins, W. J. (2021). Smoke, Mirrors and Legal Uncertainty: The Rights and Wrongs of New Zealand’s COVID-19 Response. In S. Kirchner (Ed.), *Governing the Crisis: Law, Human Rights and COVID-19* (pp.232-248). LIT Verlag.

⁸ deLisle, J. (2019).” All the World’s a Stage”: Taiwan’s Human Rights Performance and Playing to International Norms. In J. A. Cohen, W. P. Alford & C. Lo (Eds.), *Taiwan and International Human Rights: A Story of Transformation* (pp. 173-206). Springer.

According to Constitutional Court Interpretation No. 329 (1993), treaties would have the same legal status as laws only if they were concluded following procedures regulated by the Taiwanese Constitution. Due to the UN's refusal to deposit the ratifications and Taiwan's unilateral signature and inability to complete the conclusions procedure in reality, doubts have been raised about the domestic legal effect of these international treaties.⁹

Therefore, the government decided to enact Implementation Acts to clarify the legal status of domestically ratified international treaties. Besides, after the passage of the Conclusion of Treaties Act in 2015, some scholars, relying on Article 11, paragraphs 1 and 2 of the Act¹⁰, argued that even though Taiwan is not considered a contracting party under international law, treaties ratified and promulgated by the Congress still hold domestic legal effect even though they are unable to be deposited to the UN.¹¹

Below are the conventions ratified or not ratified by Taiwan.¹²

- Conventions ratified by Taiwan when it was a member of the UN before 1971: The International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (ICERD), International Labour Organization (ILO) C007, C011, C014, C015, C016, C019, C022, C023, C026, C027, C032, C045, C053, C058, C059, C073, C080, C081, C091, C095, C098, C100, C104, C105, C107, C111, C112, C113, C114, C116, C117, C118, C119, C123, C124.¹³
- Conventions signed by Taiwan in 1967 but unable to ratify before 1971, and then were incorporated into domestic law through Implementation Acts in the 2000s: ICCPR, ICESCR.

⁹ Chang, W-C. (2019). Taiwan's Human Rights Implementation Acts: A Model for Successful Incorporation?. In J. A. Cohen, W. P. Alford & C. Lo (Eds.), *Taiwan and International Human Rights: A Story of Transformation* (pp. 227-247). Springer.

¹⁰ Treaties approved by the Legislative Yuan shall be processed as follows:

(1) Treaties containing a ratification, acceptance, approval, or accession clause shall be sent by the competent authorities to the Executive Yuan to forward to the President for issuing an instrument of ratification, acceptance, approval or accession. The competent authorities shall also notify MOFA. After the domestic procedure is complete and the exchange or deposit of the instruments of the treaties in accordance with the related provisions becomes effective, the competent authorities shall send the treaties to the Executive Yuan, which shall submit them to the President for promulgation. In special cases in which an exchange or deposit of an international instrument is not possible, the competent authorities shall send the treaties to the Executive Yuan, which shall submit them to the President for promulgation.

(2) Regarding treaties without a ratification, acceptance, approval, or accession clause, the competent authorities shall send the treaties to the Executive Yuan, which will submit them to the President for reference. After the treaties become effective, the competent authorities shall send the treaties to the Executive Yuan, which shall submit them to the President for promulgation.

The treaties of the preceding paragraph have domestic legal effect from the date of promulgation.

¹¹ 黃昭元 (2015), 公民與政治權利國際公約與憲法解釋, 司法院大法官一〇四年度學術研討會: 人權公約與我國憲法解釋, 頁 107, 司法院,

<http://www.judicial.gov.tw/constitutionalcourt/FYDownload.asp?fileguid=000078-V2Q>

¹² Chang, *supra* note 9, at 230-231

¹³ 內政部編 (1967), 中華民國政府已批准之國際勞工公約, 內政部。

<https://taiwanebook.ncl.edu.tw/zh-tw/book/NCL-9910009748/reader>

- Conventions signed by Taiwan and incorporated into domestic law through Implementation Acts: CEDAW, CRC, and CRPD.
- Conventions not ratified by Taiwan: The International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families (ICMW), International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance (ICPPED), Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CAT)

1.1.2. Organization Structure: Accountability Mechanisms

Taiwan, not being a member of the UN, cannot utilize the Universal Periodic Review (UPR) to ensure compliance with the UN conventions. Due to Taiwan's unique status, the Taiwanese government could only be held accountable for international human rights by "internalizing" international human rights standards on the legislative level. Nevertheless, since Taiwan held its initial review of CEDAW in 2009¹⁴, Taiwan has established an alternative international review mechanism that involves collaboration between NGOs, scholars and experts, and the government. Since 2013, Taiwan has invited international scholars and experts with prior experience in UN treaty review to participate in the process.¹⁵ Furthermore, in response to proposals from civil society, local NGOs were invited to participate by issuing not only parallel/shadow reports that balance the views of the government but also by having a direct dialogue with international experts on various issues via sessions separate from those of the government.¹⁶

In addition to the international review mechanism, the administrative agency National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) also serves as a mechanism for supervising the domestic implementation of conventions and a channel for individuals to file complaints. Established in 2020, NHRC is a committee under the Control Yuan (introduced in 2.(2) below) that ensures the execution of human rights treaties through corrective measures and improvement requests. However, since the NHRC does not have its own Authority Exercise Act, the independence of the NHRC and its relationship with the Control Yuan remains unclear.

¹⁴ In the initial review on CEDAW, the government invited three international experts to participate in the International Review to give recommendations based on the State Report. This was regarded as a consultative conference. See Covenants Watch, 2009 Initial Review on CEDAW (Consultation), <https://en.covenantwatch.org.tw/treaty-reviews/2009-initial-review-on-cedaw-consultation/>

¹⁵ deLisle, *supra* note 8, at 194.

¹⁶ Chang, *supra* note 9, at 234.

1.1.3. Law in Practice: Applying to Emergent Conditions During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Due to the negative impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on all aspects of human life and the increased risk of human rights violations, both the international review committees and the NHRC have requested the government to comply with the international human rights treaties.

For instance, according to the review of the fourth report on the implementation of CEDAW (2022), the international review committee mentioned that there had been no gender impact assessment of the COVID-19 pandemic in Taiwan, and this issue needs to be addressed.¹⁷ The NHRC also required the government to conform to ICCPR and the COVID-19 Guidance released by the UN.¹⁸ Additionally, due to outbreaks of infections in institutions, a disability rights organization filed complaints, blaming the government for terminating institution-based services without properly providing house-based alternatives. The NHRC urges the government to implement the principles of accessibility and accommodation regulated by CRPD to safeguard the right to life of disabled people.¹⁹

In the winter of 2020/2021, the government expanded the digital fencing program, leading to concerns about the violation of individuals' privacy protection, as outlined in Article 17 of ICCPR. Considering the case number was low in January 2021, even though the actual necessity of these measures was far from clear.²⁰ In response to criticism of the expanded measure, the NHRC responded that it is necessary to balance the health rights of the entire population and privacy protection. However, the NHRC emphasized that rights to health should be given priority and is committed to reviewing government infringements on privacy after the easing of the pandemic. This indicates that the NHRC did not want to closely examine the necessity of the government's digital measures that could violate individuals' privacy rights.

¹⁷ International Review Committee (2022), Review of Taiwan's Fourth Report on the Implementation of CEDAW, Conclusions and Recommendations of the International Review Committee.

¹⁸ The National Human Rights Commission (2021/05/18), 國家人權委員會呼籲 全民發揮同理心 團結抗疫, https://www.cy.gov.tw/News_Content.aspx?n=794&s=20363

¹⁹ The National Human Rights Commission (2021/05/31), 國家人權委員會籲請重視身心障礙者因疫情加劇的多重弱勢處境, 應採取更積極措施保障其基本人權, https://nhrc.cy.gov.tw/News_Content.aspx?n=9772&sms=12362&s=1605

²⁰ The National Human Rights Commission (2021/01/04), 人權會：個人隱私為公政公約所保障, https://www.cy.gov.tw/News_Content.aspx?n=794&s=19882

1.2. National Level

1.2.1. Law on Paper: the Constitution and Legal Hierarchy

According to the Taiwanese Constitution, the central government consists of the President and five branches, including the Executive Yuan (executive), the Legislative Yuan (legislature), the Judicial Yuan (judiciary, Constitutional Court), the Control Yuan (“ombudsman”), and the Examination Yuan (qualifications of civil servants).

According to Article 171 Paragraph 1 and Article 172 of the Taiwanese Constitution, statutes inconsistent with the Constitution are void, and so are ordinances inconsistent with the Constitution or statutes. There is a clear and strict hierarchical system in the Taiwanese legal order.

1.2.2. Organizational Structure: Accountability Mechanism

1.2.2.1 The Control Yuan

The Control Yuan is the highest “ombudsman” in Taiwan, exercising the powers of impeachment, investigation, censure, corrective measures, and audit. It consists of 29 members, including a president and a vice president, each serving a six-year term. They are nominated by the President and approved by the Legislative Yuan (the Congress).

The Control Yuan is one of the main institutions in Taiwan overseeing the compliance of human rights protection by the administration. Additionally, the Control Yuan shall establish a number of committees²¹ to exercise its supervisory power (Article 96 of the Constitution).

1.2.2.2 The Legislative Yuan (the Congress)

The Legislative Yuan is the highest legislative organ of Taiwan, with the power to decide by resolution upon statutory or budgetary bills or bills concerning martial law, amnesty, declaration of war, conclusion of peace or treaties (Articles 62 and 63 of the Constitution).

The Executive Yuan (the highest executive organ) has the duty to present to the Legislative Yuan statements of its administrative policies and reports on its administration. Members of the Legislative Yuan have the right to interpellate the President and the Ministers and Chairpersons of

²¹ Standing Committees: Domestic and Ethnic Affairs, Foreign and Overseas Chinese Affairs, National Defense and Intelligence Affairs, Finance and Economic Affairs, Education and Cultural Affairs, Transportation and Procurement Affairs, Judicial and Prison Administration Affairs. The National Human Rights Committee is also a ten-member committee under the Control Yuan.

Commissions of the Executive Yuan (Article 57 of the Constitution). Therefore, the Legislative Yuan can effectively oversee government actions to ensure compliance with laws and human rights values.

There are 8 standing committees, namely the Internal Administration Committee, Social Welfare and Environmental Hygiene Committee, Judiciary and Organic Laws and Statutes Committee, Transportation Committee, Education and Culture Committee, Finance Committee, Economics Committee, and Foreign and National Defense Committee. These committees deliberate on bills according to their respective fields, overseeing whether proposed drafts from the administrative sections violate human rights regulations before being submitted for the second reading.

Additionally, the Taiwan Parliamentary Human Rights Commission is an informal subgroup in the Legislative Yuan, consisting of bipartisan legislators. Its primary goal is to enhance the exchange of international human rights protection. However, due to its informal nature, it lacks an effective oversight function.

1.2.2.3 Judicial Review

According to Articles 172 and 173 of the Constitution, illegal ordinances and unconstitutional laws shall be nullified and voided. Council of Grand Justices of the Judicial Yuan (1949-2021) and the Constitutional Court (since 2022) are in charge of interpreting the Constitution²², uniformly interpreting statutes and ordinances, and reviewing the constitutionality of laws. This judicial review mechanism ensures the constitutionality, especially the protection of fundamental rights, of all government actions.

1.2.3. Law in Practice: The Accountability mechanism & the Government's Human Rights Justification During the COVID-19 Pandemic

On January 11, 2020, Taiwan conducted both presidential and legislative elections. The incumbent president, Tsai Ing-Wen of the Democratic Progressive Party (DPP), won the presidential election. In the legislative election, the Kuomintang (Chinese Nationalist Party) obtained only 38 of all 113 seats, and the DPP won 61 seats, keeping its congressional majority.

²² Taiwan's Constitutional Court (TCC) used to be called “Grand Justices of the Judicial Yuan”(司法院大法官) before the enactment of the Constitutional Court Procedure Act (CCPA), which took effect on January 4, 2022. Until 2022, Grand Justices, in the form of “constitutional interpretation”, held the exclusive power to review the constitutionality of legal statutes, but not court decisions. Since the CCPA took effect in 2022, the TCC turned into a “constitutional court” in a strict sense. The CCPA introduced a constitutional complaint system, which authorized TCC to review court decisions. *See* The Judicial Yuan (2021/01/15), *The Taiwan Constitutional Court in a New Era*, <https://www.judicial.gov.tw/en/cp-2083-358640-47e30-2.html>; Lin, C-C. (2022). The Pros and Cons of Taiwan's Constitutional Court Procedure Act. *USALI Perspectives*, 2(17). <https://usali.org/usali-perspectives-blog/the-pros-and-cons-of-taiwans-constitutional-court-procedure-act>.

Taiwan's COVID-19 response began already in the beginning of January 2020. As there would be no transition of power after the 2020 election, and the DPP would continue to have the majority in Congress, the Special Act for Prevention, Relief and Revitalization Measures for Severe Pneumonia with Novel Pathogens (hereinafter referred to as the Special Act) was promptly promulgated in February 2020. This legislation, enacted specially to authorize administrative responses to emergencies during the COVID-19 pandemic, granted the Central Epidemic Command Center (CECC) the power to "take all necessary actions." This provision established broad authorization for the administration and remained unmodified until the implementation period of the Special Act expired on 30 June 2023.²³ The Congress had not exercised significant checking power because the majority party, the DPP, was the same party in the administration.²⁴

As we will explain below, the oversight of the power of the above-mentioned supervisory mechanism had weakened during the COVID-19 pandemic. While the oversight mechanism does exist, most of the oversight organs voluntarily relinquished their checking power, despite facing significant criticism from civil society regarding the government's measures. In a few incidents and cases, the government utilized human rights justifications to respond to the criticism. To explore the reasons behind the government's reliance on human rights justifications, we will analyze the reality of its accountability and whether it utilized human rights discourses.

2.2.3.1 Weakened Legislative Oversight & Article 7 of the Special Act for Prevention, Relief and Revitalization Measures for Severe Pneumonia with Novel Pathogens

According to Article 7 of the Special Act, the Commander of the CECC, for disease prevention and control requirements, implements necessary response actions or measures. This provision is a general clause that broadly delegates the CECC to implement necessary actions and measures in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The CECC mechanism was initially established ad hoc in 2003 during the SARS outbreak and was later institutionalized. On January 20, 2020, the CECC, headed by the Ministry of Health and Welfare and its affiliate, the Taiwan Centers for Disease Control (CDC), was established in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. As the pandemic developed, the Executive Yuan gradually leveled up the CECC, first on January 23 and then elevated it to the highest level on February 27. It was the first time the CECC was upgraded to the highest level since its mechanism was introduced in 2003.

²³ When the Special Act was enacted in 2020, it contained a sunset clause to terminate on 30 June, 2021. The Special Act was amended in 2021 and 2022, and the sunset clause was extended for a year each time.

²⁴ Lin, M-H. (2021), Revisiting the Constitutionality Controversies of Special Act for Prevention, Relief and Revitalization Measures for Severe Pneumonia with Novel Pathogens Article 7, *Taiwan Law Journal*, 407, 53-67. Hsieh, C.-W., Wang, M., Wong, N. W., & Ho, L. K. (2021). A whole-of-nation approach to COVID-19: Taiwan's National Epidemic Prevention Team. *International Political Science Review*, 42(3), 300–315. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01925121211012291>

Due to the broad authority of legislation and vague definition of "for disease prevention and control requirements," concerns have arisen regarding the violation of the principle of explicit delegation. As a result, following the passage of the Special Act in February 2020, Article 7 was immediately criticized by legal scholars and civil organizations. However, as the disease seemed to have been effectively controlled, especially when compared to the pandemic development in other countries during 2020, the criticisms of Article 7 were only sporadic.

In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic only had a small impact in Taiwan, with the overwhelming majority of confirmed cases being imported and only sporadic community transmissions. Nevertheless, in May 2021, a small-scale community transmission erupted. Even though the case number was low (the highest daily number was around 700), as it was the first outbreak in Taiwan since 2020, the government responded promptly to control the spread. The government requested Congress to review proposed amendments to Articles 11 and 19 of the Special Act, which aimed to extend and increase the budget for the Special Act on May 21.²⁵ As the legislative session ended in May²⁶, Congress passed the proposed amendments on May 31 without much deliberation.²⁷ Despite legislators proposing 203 incidental resolutions to the amendment of Articles 11 and 19, incidental resolutions lack binding force and only serve to demonstrate legislators' concerns about these matters.²⁸

It is evident that legislative oversight was weak during the pandemic. As the ruling DPP holds the majority of Congress, Congress became not much more than a rubber stamp. Despite the knowledge of COVID-19 increased and the clarity of international epidemic control standards grew over time, there was no corresponding increase in congressional supervision. Notably, in Oct 2021, 23 KMT legislators proposed to amend Article 7 to restrict the power of the CECC, but the amendment did not even pass the committee review before the second reading.²⁹

²⁵ Legislative Yuan Official Gazette (2022). 110 (60) No. 4911: 1-2; Legislative Yuan, 13 Sittings, 10th Appointed Dates, 3th Session, *Agenda Related Documents No. 1905*, https://lis.ly.gov.tw/lygazettec/mtdoc?PD100313:LCEWA01_100313_00007.

²⁶ According to Article 68 of the Constitution, the Legislative Yuan should hold two sessions each year, and should convene of its own accord. The first session lasts from February to the end of May, and the second session from September to the end of December.

²⁷ Legislative Yuan Official Gazette (2022). 110(66) No. 4917: 223-272.

²⁸ Legislative Yuan (2004), *Principles and Institutions of Legisprudence*, 20.

²⁹ The 23 KMT legislators criticized Article 7 for its ambiguous wording and lack of clear standards. The amendment bill would raise the bar for the CECC's power to take necessary response actions or measures only when the community transmission became uncontrollable. The bill would also mandate the establishment of a committee for decision making and must have all decisions in writing. As the DPP had a majority in Congress and held one of the two seats of the conveners of the Social Welfare and Environmental Hygiene Committee (each committee has two conveners), the DPP managed to exclude the KMT bill from the agenda, blocking it from entering the voting process. One should also note that since the amendment was proposed by separate legislators rather than the KMT Party Caucus, it can be inferred that there was no clear consensus on the amendment within the opposition party either.

Legislative Yuan, 4 Sittings, 10th Appointed Dates, 4th Session, *Agenda Related Documents No. 1805*, https://lis.ly.gov.tw/lygazettec/mtdoc?PD100403:LCEWA01_100403_00031; Legislative Yuan (2012),

Although Art 7 was criticized by legal scholars and human rights advocacy groups since the Special Act was first promulgated in February 2020, it was not until September 2021 that the CECC finally responded to these criticisms. The CECC emphasized that only eight measures were implemented under the authority delegated by Article 7. These included orders prohibiting teachers, students, and medical workers from traveling abroad, extending the term for migrant workers to stay in Taiwan, and suspending the convening of annual shareholder meetings, among others. The CECC argued that revising laws would be too time-consuming and inadequate to respond to the emergency situation. They insisted that most of the other actions and measures were delegated by Article 37 of the Communicable Disease Control Act³⁰, which, in their interpretation, also grants broad authorization to the administration if they find an actual need to prevent communicable diseases from spreading.³¹

This reflects a broad discretion of the administration during the pandemic. By literally interpreting the clauses with broad authorization, the government appropriated the language of the rule of law to legitimize its extraordinary pandemic response measures.

2.2.3.2 The Pandemic Outbreak of Wanhua District & National Health Insurance Card Annotation

When conducting contact tracing during the May 2021 outbreak, it was revealed that several confirmed cases had visited a hostess tea house in the red-light district in Wanhua, Taipei, when they were infectious. The number of reported cases in this district went up to more than 100 for three days in mid-May (with one day exceeding 170), but dropped to under 50 after late-May and then

Introduction to the legislative procedure,
<https://www.ly.gov.tw/EngPages/Detail.aspx?nodeid=335&pid=43232>.

³⁰ Article 37 of the Communicable Disease Control Act: When communicable diseases occur or are expected to occur, local competent authorities shall, by considering actual needs, take the following measures in collaboration with organizations (institutions) concerned:

- 1.regulate schooling, meeting, gathering or other group activities;
- 2.regulate entry and exit of people to and from specific places and restrict the number of people admitted;
- 3.regulate traffic in specific areas;
- 4.evacuate people from specific places or areas;
- 5.restrict or prohibit patients or suspected patients with communicable diseases from traveling by means of public transportation or entering/leaving specific places;
- 6.other disease control measures announced by government organizations at various levels.

Organizations (institutions), groups, enterprises and individuals shall not refuse, evade or obstruct the abovementioned measures.

Measures mentioned in Paragraph 1 that shall be taken by local competent authorities shall be implemented during the period when the central epidemic command center is in existence in accordance with instructions of its commander.

³¹ 謝君臨 (2021/09/30), 防疫特別條例「霸王條款」石崇良: 1年多來僅用8次, 自由時報, <https://news.ltn.com.tw/news/politics/breakingnews/3688759>

stayed under 20 from mid-June 2021.³² Although the scale of the outbreak may be small on the global scale, it was the largest outbreak in Taiwan since the pandemic began in 2020 and the Wanhua area was the largest cluster. To control the spread, the CECC identified Wanhua as a high-risk area.

Based on cell site location information provided by telecommunications service providers, approximately 600,000 "epidemic alert text messages" were sent to people who had entered or exited the Wanhua area during specific periods. Among them, the CECC further used cell tower data (e.g. time of entry and exit) to identify about 150,000 people as potential employees of customers of businesses in the area and annotated their NHI card without informing them.³³

To criticize the NHI annotation for people who had digital traces in Wanhua, the Control Yuan delivered an investigation report, indicating that the NHI card annotation incident was questionable in terms of procedures and administrative transparency, and has led to discrimination and stigmatization of Wanhua. The report utilized the UN human rights guidelines and the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to criticize the government for its lack of informing and announcements. Despite the government's excessive measures, the Control Yuan merely expressed concern about the violation of human rights and the principle of the rule of law. It appears that the Control Yuan relinquished its checking power and merely issued a caution to the government. As it did not go further to use its power of corrective measures³⁴, the government was allowed to respond perfunctorily.

The CECC insisted that the NHI card annotation is necessary for controlling the spread and responded to the criticism in two aspects. First, the CECC stated that it was not the first time they used NHI card annotation to prevent an epidemic. NHI annotations were made for Taiwanese citizens with a travel history to China as early as 2020. As the pandemic escalated globally, annotations were also made for people returning from other countries.³⁵ Second, the CECC emphasized that the NHI annotation was not intended to stigmatize people who traveled or lived in Wanhua, but rather to safeguard the rights to health/personal safety of medical workers and patients and to protect public health. To the CECC, annotation provided medical workers with sufficient information to respond effectively, making medical assessment much easier.³⁶

³² Taipei, Wanhua district- COVID-19 daily confirmed cases, https://covid-19.nchc.org.tw/2023_town_confirmed.php?mycity=%E5%8F%B0%E5%8C%97%E5%B%82&mytown=%E8%90%AC%E8%8F%AF%E5%8D%80

³³ 謝幸恩、洪玲玲（2021/05/26），【獨家】內部文件曝光！指揮中心竟密令監測萬華 60 萬人足跡 挑出「高風險族群」註記健保卡，壹傳媒，<https://yimedia.com.tw/investigate/117647/>（最後瀏覽日：2023 年 11 月 27 日）。

³⁴ 監察院（2022/05/27），調查報告，111 社調，0006<https://www.cy.gov.tw/CyBsBoxContent.aspx?n=133&s=17787>

³⁵ 盧逸峰（2021/05/28），健保卡註記「萬華旅遊史」挨轟侵害人權 指揮中心：早有先例，風傳媒，<https://www.storm.mg/article/3709624>

³⁶ 王芊凌（2021/05/27），疫情即時／在萬華的民眾健保卡遭註記！指揮中心：加速醫療院所研判，HEHO，<https://heho.com.tw/archives/175862>

Behind the rhetoric of protecting the rights to health/personal safety of medical workers, the main purpose of the government was likely to ensure the overall healthcare manpower and capacity. The government, in fact, showed little concern for the rights to health of medical workers after they contracted COVID-19, as evident from the minimal number of occupational injuries applied and granted.

Even though medical workers contracting COVID-19 fall within the scope of compensation for occupational injuries, the actual number of applicants was extremely low. With around 150,000 medical workers in Taiwan and a nationwide infection rate of approximately 17.8%, a conservative estimation of confirmed cases among medical workers should be nearly 26,000.³⁷ However, as of August 2022, the Taipei Physicians Union reported that only 569 medical workers had applied for occupational injury compensation in the past two years amid the pandemic.³⁸ Furthermore, nearly 50 percent of medical workers indicated that the infection within their hospitals was over 30%, suggesting that the estimate of 26,000 confirmed cases is underestimated.³⁹ The low rate of applicants is attributed to unclear procedures for occupational injury compensation and the deliberate obstacles created by medical institutions, such as requiring medical workers contracted COVID-19 to prove that they were infected at work. Despite protests from the labor union, there was a lack of visible proactive oversight from the Ministry of Health and Welfare and the Ministry of Labor. Public health considerations seem to have been prioritized over the health of medical workers.

Additionally, it's worth noting that even before the COVID-19 pandemic, doctors traveling abroad were subject to the NHI card annotation. The NHI uses a point system to reimburse doctors for the medical services they provide. As an accounting measure in Taiwan's health insurance system, doctors' immigration records are linked with the NHI database to prevent fraud, i.e., doctors' reported medical services will be checked against their travel history. The NHI annotation during the COVID-19 pandemic helped to highlight this long standing privacy concern that has long existed in the NHI system.

2.2.3.3 Quarantine Measures & Court's Decisions

In 2020, Taiwan implemented strict border control and compulsory quarantine measures, restricting the personal freedom of millions. Due to the passage of the Habeas Corpus Act in 2014, people whose personal freedom has been restricted by authorities other than the court can petition to the court for relief, and the court must review the disposition at issue within 48 hours. For those who bore the cost of this restriction on personal freedom, petitions under the Habeas Corpus Act became a channel for seeking an administrative remedy. The courts' perspectives on the

³⁷ 李秉芳 (2022/07/15), 工會估 2.6 萬醫護曾染疫, 僅 465 人申請職災給付: 院方阻撓刁難, 要求證明「因公確診」, 關鍵評論網, <https://www.thenewslens.com/article/169683>

³⁸ 賴淑敏、邱福財 (2022/07/15), 醫護難申請職災傷病給付 工會籲政府提具體改善措施, 公視新聞網, <https://news.pts.org.tw/article/590400>

³⁹ 李秉芳, *supra* note 37.

government's restriction of personal freedom will also have an impact on the rule of law post-pandemic.

There were 92 court decisions from July 2020 to July 2022, and three-quarters of them were petitioned by airline pilots who frequently entered and exited the border as part of their job.⁴⁰ One of the issues was whether quarantine at home or hotel counts as detention and gives rise to habeas corpus claim. In the first two years, the administrative court generally declined to offer any substantive examination during the habeas corpus review process and found the administrative dispositions valid based on formality. Petitioners who reckoned their arrest or detention to be illegal would have to appeal through the administrative litigation procedure, which would take much longer than the quarantine period. Therefore, the administrative court ended up throwing out these cases as the plaintiffs would have been freed of quarantine and lacked standing when the cases were decided. Hence, the personal freedom right under the Habeas Corpus Act failed to provide any redress.

It was not until January 2022 that the Taipei High Administrative Court broadened the scope of the Habeas Corpus Act review and went beyond formality when reviewing a case brought by a pilot. In its ruling, the court declared that home quarantine fell under the category of “detention” as defined by the Habeas Corpus Act, and examined the substantive legality of administrative dispositions, which were declined by the administrative court mentioned above.

This Taipei High Administrative Court’s opinion addressed questions that were left unanswered by the decision of Constitutional Court Interpretation No. 690 (2011). Interpretation No. 690 (2011) was ambiguous about whether mandatory quarantine fell under the category of “detention”. Interpretation No. 690 decided that an individual's freedom is deprived when subjected to mandatory quarantine for medical reasons, but mandatory quarantine for medical reasons is different from criminal punishment in nature and a more lenient test can be permitted.⁴¹ Yet, Interpretation No. 690 did not specifically say whether non-criminal mandatory quarantine measures can be considered “detention” and whether petitions for habeas corpus relief are applicable. In this case, the Taipei High Administrative broadened its review of the Habeas Corpus Act, indicating that the court’s oversight of mandatory quarantine has shifted from lenient to more stringent.

Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that in 2023, Taiwan's Constitutional Court (TCC) dismissed a case regarding Article 7 of the Special Act. As mentioned, this article grants broad authorization to the administration, potentially violating the principle of explicit delegation. In January 2023, a judge from the High Administrative Court requested the TCC to review the constitutionality of Article 7, considering it as the legal basis for school closure orders. The case involved a teacher who faced

⁴⁰ Lin, S-R. (2023). An Analysis of Courts' Decisions on Petitions for Habeas Corpus by Quarantined National Airline Pilots, *The Journal of Science & Health Law*, 28(1), 41-91.

⁴¹ Constitutional Court (2011/09/30). Interpretation No.690 (Compulsory Quarantine and Personal Liberty and Security Case), <https://cons.judicial.gov.tw/en/docdata.aspx?fid=100&id=310871>

administrative discipline for violating the school closure order and organizing a video shooting on campus for a graduating class. The TCC determined that the teacher received an admonition in accordance with the Teacher's Evaluation Regulation, and concluded that the Special Act was not relevant in this case. Based on their reasoning on purely procedural language and reasoning, the TCC refused to review the constitutionality of the Special Act and the blank slate authorization in Article 7 and voluntarily relinquished its oversight power.

2. Civil Society Engagement

To fully comprehend how the Taiwanese government interprets and frames the concept of human rights, especially in the context of the pandemic, it's crucial to include the responses from civil society. This necessitates an investigation into the roles of NGOs and the social groups from civil society.

In the first year of the project, we had initial conversations with NGOs on general human rights issues. This aims to grasp their interaction with both international covenants and the European Union and to what extent and how these interactions influence their work. In the civil society engagement in the second year, we will communicate our findings in the first year with experts, advocates, and people affected by the COVID-19 measures. We will focus on three groups of people who were particularly affected by the COVID-19 governance in Taiwan: healthcare workers, flight crew members, and local epidemic prevention personnel. Through focus groups, we aim to understand their observations regarding the government's epidemic control measures, governance, and the direct impacts they've experienced during this period.